

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

MODERNIZATION OF PETROL CLEANING PLANT WITH DEVELOPMENT OF RECTIFICATION COLUMN

Lytvyn O.,
graduate student

Stepaniuk A.

associate professor, Ph.D

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7437503>

Abstract

A description of the distillation column is given. The main advantages and disadvantages of the existing apparatus are determined. It is proposed to modernize the existing apparatus to improve the efficiency of benzene purification.

Keywords: benzene, rectification column, modernization, cap, plate.

Benzene, or phenyl hydrogen is an organic chemical compound with the molecular formula C_6H_6 . The benzene molecule is composed of six carbon atoms joined in a planar ring with one hydrogen atom attached to each. Because it contains only carbon and hydrogen atoms, benzene is classed as a hydrocarbon.

The main structure in the purification of benzene is the rectification column.

Rectification column is designed for separation of liquid mixtures, components of which feature different boiling points. The rectification column refers to a vertical cylinder with contact devices mounted inside [1].

Distilling liquid vapors are supplied to the distillation columns. They rise from below, and in the counter flow mode, the liquid that condenses at the top in the refrigerator goes to meet the vapors. In the case where the depressant consists of two components, the final

products are the distillate coming from the top of the column and the bottom residue. The situation becomes more complicated if it is necessary to separate a mixture consisting of a large number of fractions [2].

The aim of the diploma project is to modernize the rectification column. Advantages:

High productivity;

Simplicity of design.

Disadvantages:

In the event of an emergency increase in steam consumption, the column stops working efficiently:

This disadvantage of the column is proposed to be eliminated because of to the installation of a cover on the cap, which, in case of an emergency increase in steam, rises and the excess steam escapes.

The figure 1 shows us the scheme of the modernized cap of the rectification column.

1 – body of the plate, 2 – tube, 3 – slits, 4 – canal, 5 – plate (modernization), 6 – cap, 7 – nut

Figure 1 – the scheme of the column cap modernization.

On the figure 2 you can see 3D model of our cap.

Figure 2 – 3D model of the column cap modernization

To be sure in this modernization we put the cap in special tube and made a flow simulation. The figure 3 shows us air speed with closed plate.

Figure 3 – Flow simulation with closed plate

The figure 4 shows us air speed with closed plate.

Figure 4 – Flow simulation with opened plate

This simulation shows us that opened plate helps excess steam to go through the cap. Steam consumption increased by 20% with a sharp increase in costs

In this way, the disadvantage of the rectification column was eliminated and the reliability of the design and the safety of the benzene purification process were ensured.

References:

1. <https://bts.net.ua/eng/column/column2/>
2. https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ректифікаційна_колонна